

ISic1508

I.Sicily inscription 1508

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacombs of S. Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ὑπ[ατεία]

2. τῶν κυρίων [ἡμῶν] Κωνστ(αντίου) Σεβασ[τ τὸ --- καὶ ---]

Apparatus

Text after Ferrua 1982-1983

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645009

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0861

Ferrua, A 1982-1983. Le iscrizioni datate della Sicilia paleocristiana. *Kokalos*. 28-29: 3-29. At 4 no.1

Agnello, S.L. 1960. Iscrizioni cimiteriali inedite di Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana*. 36: 19-42. At 30 no.27 fig.3

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